

Investigation of Structural and Mechanical Properties Of 3D Printed Bamboo-like Microstructures

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Overall View

- Introduction of bamboo
- Vascular bundles of bamboo
- 3D printed continuous fibers
- Bio-inspired design through 3D printing
- Structural and mechanical characterization

Introduction of bamboo

- Giant grass with wood characteristics
- 75 genera, over 1200 species
- Very fast growth rate
- Without secondary growth

Giant bamboo forest [3]

Inspiration from Nature

Specific strength and stiffness for both natural and synthetic materials [1]

Relationship of tensile strength and fracture toughness for engineering materials [2]

Vascular Bundles of Bamboo

Hierarchical microstructure of bamboo [4]

Mechanical properties of bamboo

Vascular bundle distribution [5]

- **Number:** Gradient increased
- **Shape:** Circular to oval
- **Size:** 2.5 times ratio relationship

Structural display of VB [6]

Bamboo's Failure

Microhardness indentation-induced crack growth transverse view [7]

Tensile failure induced crack growth longitudinal view [7]

- Crack propagate in a tortuous way through vascular bundles
- The interfacial fractures are responsible for the remarkable fracture toughness

Stress distributions induced in bamboo structure due to bending moment [8]

Photoelastic test for radial and hoop direction [8]

Wide range of application for 3D printing

Innovations in Healthcare [9]

Auto-mobile [10]

Fashion&Design [11]

Construction [12]

Micro

Macro

Common methods for 3D printing: FFF, SLA, SLM, SLS

Main Challenge in FDM 3D printing

Polymer sintering process [16]

Main influential factors :

- Raster angle
- Layer thickness
- Filament feed rate
- Temperature

Micrographs and schematics of two different meso-structures, a) rectangular and b) skewed, showing typical triangular void formation [13]

FDM tool path parameters [14]

3D Printing Composite

- Almost eliminated material waste
- Mold required for AFP
- Various methods to print continuous fibers

<https://www.nonplanar.xyz/>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gmePlcUOTRw&t=209s>

Matsuzaki, Ryosuke, Scientific reports (2016)

<http://www.automateddynamics.com/about-us>

Camirero M A, Polymer Testing, 2018, 68: 415-423.

Limitations and Findings

- There are different ways of printing continuous fibers, but it has advantages and disadvantages
- It would be promising if more efforts can be paid for improving the existing slicing software

<https://markforged.com/>
<https://anisoprint.com/>

Typical vascular bundle of bamboo [16]

Simplification
→

Screen shot model from eiger slicing software

Structural characterization

- Designed volume fraction
 - V(Glass): 21.16%
 - V(Pores): 12.83%
- Fiber direction : 0 °

Transverse and longitudinal view of X-ray

Structural Visualization

- Voids inside fiber bundles
- Fiber misalignment found
- Voids found in cutting position during printing process

- Volume Fraction
 - V (Glass): 20.07%
 - V (Pores): 28.42%
- Fiber Misalignment
 - In plane: 2.6 °
 - Out of plane: 12 °

Impact Resistance Result

Layout 1

Layout 2

Layout 3

Category	Pure Nylon	Layout1 Vf = 25%	layout2 Vf = 25%	layout3 Vf = 25%
Impact strength (kJ/m ²)	5.9	75.6	27.9	73.1
Weight (g)	7.97	13.01	13.05	10.55

- Highly anisotropic for 3D printed material
- Fiber bundle shape has influence on impact resistance of 3D printed material

Impact resistance result

Energy Absorption Mechanism:

- Fiber breakage
- Fiber pull-out
- Delamination
- Fiber bundle debonding

Impact resistance result

Energy Absorption Mechanism:

- Fiber breakage
- Fiber pullout

Inspiration from nature

Energy absorption:

- Fiber breakage
- Fiber pullout
- Delamination
- Matrix plastic deformation

Conclusion

- There are different ways of printing continuous fibers, but it has advantages and disadvantages
- The real printed material can vary from the original design in software
- Spatial distribution of fiber bundles have an influence on mechanical properties of printed structure

References

- [1] Wegst, Ulrike GK, et al. "Bioinspired structural materials." *Nature materials* 14.1 (2015): 23.
- [2] Libonati, Flavia, and Markus J. Buehler. "Advanced structural materials by bioinspiration." *Advanced Engineering Materials* (2017): 1600787.
- [3] <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/blog/agriculture/the-story-of-national-bamboo-mission-61016>
- [4] Wegst U G, Bai H, Saiz E, et al. Bioinspired structural materials. [J]. *Nature Materials*, 2015, 14(1):23-36.
- [5] Kanzawa E, Aoyagi S, Nakano T. Vascular bundle shape in cross-section and relaxation properties of Moso bamboo (*Phyllostachys pubescens*)[J]. *Materials Science & Engineering C*, 2011, 31(5):1050-1054.
- [6] Li, Hongbo, and Shengping Shen. "The mechanical properties of bamboo and vascular bundles." *Journal of Materials Research* 26.21 (2011): 2749-2756.
- [6] Shao, Zhuoping, and Fuli Wang. *The Fracture Mechanics of Plant Materials: Wood and Bamboo*. Springer, 2018.
- [7] Habibi, Meisam K., and Yang Lu. "Crack propagation in bamboo's hierarchical cellular structure." *Scientific reports* 4 (2014): 5598.
- [8] Nogata, Fumio, and Hideaki Takahashi. "Intelligent functionally graded material: bamboo." *Composites Engineering* 5.7 (1995): 743-751.
- [9] <https://qz.com/1596522/scientists-say-they-just-created-the-worlds-first-3d-printed-heart/>
- [10] <https://www.google.com/url?sa=i&source=images&cd=&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=2ahUKEwi01LeM0ZTiAhWq4IUkHS6BDo8Qjhx6BAgBEAM&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.md-3d.com%2Fnews%2F124.html&psig=AOvVaw324Td4wsLt41rDmopBAKU&ust=1557703821120084>
- [11] <https://3dprint.com/177436/interior-design-3d-printing/>
- [12] <https://popupcity.net/worlds-first-3d-apartment-complex-printed-in-china/>
- [13] Matsuzaki, Ryosuke, et al. "Three-dimensional printing of continuous-fiber composites by in-nozzle impregnation." *Scientific reports* 6 (2016): 23058.
- [14] https://static.markforged.com/markforged_composites_datasheet.pdf.
- [15] <https://www.nlr.org/news/nlr-wins-award-for-new-fibre-placement-processes/>
- [16] DENİZ, İlhan, et al. "Kraft and modified kraft pulping of bamboo (*Phyllostachys bambusoides*)." *Drewno: prace naukowe, doniesienia, komunikaty* 60 (2017).

Obrigado

Спасибо!

Thanks

Grazie

谢谢!